

HOW TO IMPROVE PRODUCTIVE SKILLS WITH THE HELP OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGY

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Annotation: This article is devoted to the planning of teaching language to students who have it as a non-native language with the help of modern pedagogical technologies (in our case interactive whiteboard) and offers an intensive course to improve the skills and competence of teachers in the field of innovation. Modern man should consider education as a means of implementing their own educational, professional, cultural and life plans, as well as a way of forming key competencies, the ability to apply their knowledge and skills in parallel with the innovation of the XXI century, ensuring the success of all human activity.

Key words: productive skills, speaking, writing, interactive whiteboard, innovation, education, method, competence, modern, pedagogical technologies, teacher, student.

The productive skills are speaking and writing, because learners doing these need to produce language. They are also known as active skills. They can be compared with the receptive skills of listening and reading. However, today's world requires that the goal of teaching speaking should improve students' communicative skills, because, only in that way, students can express themselves and learn how to follow the social and cultural rules appropriate in each communicative circumstance. In the preliminary stage, teachers used tape recorders as a technological device to instruct the students, which later evolved as communication laboratory. The integration of technology into language teaching which was started in the early 1960s and 1970s, assisted teachers to teach second language learners how to speak in the best way possible. Every day teachers are getting access to some new

technologies, which join hand with English teaching. As the conventional teaching method such as the chalk and talk method seems to be outdated, the modern technologies can be used as a supplement to the classroom teaching method to have a lively atmosphere in the classroom. New technologies in language learning by multiple intelligence and mixed abilities replace with old methods of teaching. Technology can stimulate the playfulness of learners and immerse them in a variety of scenarios. Technology gives learners a chance to engage in self-directed actions, opportunities for self-paced interactions, privacy, and a safe environment in which errors get corrected and specific feedback is given. Feedback by a machine offers additional value by its ability to track mistakes and link the student immediately to exercises that focus on specific errors. When links are provided to locate explanations, additional help, and reference, the value of technology is further augmented. Modern technologies available in education today are: Communication lab, Speech recognition software, Internet, TELL (Technology Enhanced Language Learning), Pod casting, Quick Link Pen, Quicktionary. Communication labs are available to develop speaking skills. By incorporating suitable software through computers the students will play it again and again with their own interest and try to improve their speaking skills, which are most essential in this modernized IT world [3, p.473]. The usage of headphones in the lab makes the students to have interest over the subject and induces them to repeat again and again instead of feeling boredom. Speech recognition software also helps improving the students speaking, this can convert spoken words to machine-readable input. The device recognizes the accuracy of what was read and then provides a positive reinforcement like “You sound great!” or gives the user an opportunity to try again, in this way the learner can figure if he is reading well or not. As the user’s skill improves, the technology reads less material so that the learner reads more. This software also evaluates and provides scores of grammar, pronunciation, comprehension and provided with the correct forms, for examples if a student mispronounces a word, the learning tool can immediately spot it and help correct it. Internet is a commonly acknowledged term

and widely used by people throughout the world. Students now use Internet in the class to learn English. Online teaching inside the classroom seems to be interesting and makes the students to find out the suitable materials for them. Internet is a commonly acknowledged term and widely used by people throughout the world. Students now use Internet in the class to learn English. Online teaching inside the classroom seems to be interesting and makes the students to find out the suitable materials for them [4, p. 281]. TELL is the use of computer technology including hardware, software and the internet to enhance teaching and learning of languages. It allows the students to get access with all the technologies available for the enhancement of English learning. Students are allowed to use online dictionaries, chat, and to view the various happenings around the world. Podcasts can be uploaded or downloaded, this audio help the learner familiarize with the target language and teachers can use them as useful audio material that can be used in class for activities like discussions, besides, in the web. Podcast undoubtedly help learners in speaking. Pod casting is the integration of audio files where we can feed our own materials and ply it inside and outside of the classroom. Students use i-pods to hear their favorite music files. In the same way they have their education in the form of entertainment. Podcasting allows students to use their tech-based entertainment systems for educational purposes. Using technology in learning English language has become a real necessity nowadays. This paper has reviewed briefly how technology can be utilized in developing the speaking skill of the learners. Different methods for using technology in improving speaking skill were discussed thoroughly.

Currently, Uzbekistan has begun intensive introduction of modern information technologies in the education process. Effective use during classes, as separate virtual stands, and electronic textbooks and various multimedia programs-developments. The main way to implement the objectives of education is the use of various modern pedagogical technologies. Each of these technologies contributes to the development of the student's personality, to his socialization. The organization

and implementation of them is subject to didactic principles: scientific; accessibility; consistency; communication theory with practice; visibility; comprehensive development of personality [7-12]. Therefore, every teacher should strive to achieve grammatical correctness of students' speech. Every year the role of audiovisual and interactive technologies increases, they become an integral part of the modern educational process, but they can be used in conjunction with traditional teaching methods. Thus, we should not forget that one of the main tasks in the lesson is the formation of students' strong knowledge, skills and abilities. The interactive whiteboard allows to combine innovative and traditional methods of teaching the Russian language. Whiteboard, chalk, task cards, and paper posters are component parts of pedagogical technology that have been good in the past. Traditional chalkboard is no longer able to cope with the new features. The new generation that grew up on computers and mobile phones, which has a much higher need for visual information require a different approach from the teacher. Modern whiteboard should be interactive-this conclusion comes to everyone who is faced with increasing requirements for the organization and information content of the school process. Interactive whiteboards in practice are much more effective than traditional whiteboards or projectors. Due to the fact that the material is submitted in an interactive mode, the communicative interaction with students is significantly improved, which allows to bring information to them faster and more effectively. Accordingly, the quality of education is improving. Teachers, in their work to optimize the educational process on the basis of new information technologies, use a computer in different ways: in pairs on the Russian language and literature or in research work with students. In our opinion, the use of interactive whiteboard is not necessary for each pair, due to the specifics of the subject "Russian language" or "Literature". The teacher, depending on the topic, the type of classes, goals, can refer to the possibilities of an interactive whiteboard only when the effectiveness and expediency of such work is obvious and gives the result. The use of interactive whiteboard at the stage of explaining new material is effective for students whose

Russian language is not their native language. And also it allows each student according to its leading channel of perception (audial, kinesthetic, visual) to choose that form of the task by means of which he will master educational material quicker and easier. The theoretical material of the paragraph can be presented in the form of diagrams, tables [13-18]. Visual information, independent drawing up of the scheme or filling of the table forms ability of trained to analyze, allocate the main thing, to generalize, laconically to state thoughts. Develop auditory, visual and motor types of memory. With the help of an interactive whiteboard, you can actively involve students in the process of mastering the material, improve the pace and course of the lesson. Russian language teachers know how difficult it is for students for whom Russian is not their native language to memorize vocabulary words. An interactive whiteboard also helps in this work. The screen displays a dictionary word to memorize spelling, given its etymology, lexical meaning. Students can make phrases as independently in a notebook, and on a Board, to write down one-root words, Registration of dictionary words as hyperlinks allows to create dictionaries of various types: thematic, spelling, orthopedic. Work on creation of pages in such dictionaries I charge also to students as the individual differentiated homework. This increases motivation to study the subject, activity on the pair. The use of an interactive whiteboard when working with text opens up wide opportunities. I prepare the text in advance and use it for versatile analysis: lexical, spelling, punctuation. In the text, letters can be omitted, punctuation marks that need to be inserted, words, phrases, sentences that need to be paid special attention can be highlighted. It is convenient to perform types of grammatical parsing. It is possible to present the text unconventionally: different font and color of letters attracts the attention of students, develops spelling vigilance [19]. At the stage of consolidation of the studied I demonstrate questions with correct answers, opened in stages. A good assistant Board and on pairs development speech. The student when working with an interactive whiteboard not only sees and perceives, he experiences emotions. Visual, always in front of the eyes of the information helps to focus on key points

and actively engage visual memory. On the pairs of preparation for the essay or essay demonstrate reproductions of paintings by famous artists, carry out the selection of working materials (words, phrases). It is possible to present the rich didactic material at definition of signs of style of speech, the basic thought, at the analysis of figuratively-expressive means of communication of sentences in the text. Interactive whiteboard is not fundamentally new in pedagogy; it is a transformation of an ordinary whiteboard, only an improved form. Back in 1891. Russian teacher and psychologist Kapterev P.F noted: "Knowledge, of course, valuable, but even more valuable skill, art, ability. Knowledge in itself, apart from the development of the mind, is of very little importance in education: one does not learn everything, one does not learn all the Sciences. It is important that a person can learn what he needs. The most important acquisition of students is the ability to think and speak correctly, the ability to learn". The ideas of Kapterev P.F. formed the basis of the method of projects developed by. Blonsky P.P, who wrote: "in school, the child first of all should not learn theoretical knowledge, but learn to live. And the school should become a place of life of the child, should create the rational organization of this life at which the pupil not only learns, but also exercises in independent knowledge. To live is to know reality and transform it". In this regard, the interactive whiteboard becomes one of the leading modern technologies in the practice of teaching the Russian language. Its main idea is as follows: with great enthusiasm, the child performs only the activities that are chosen by him. The interactive whiteboard is based on the development of cognitive skills of students, the ability to independently design and use their knowledge, the ability to navigate in the information space and critically comprehend the information received. Thus, we can highlight the advantage of an interactive whiteboard: • Interactive whiteboard allows you to create and improve your own collections of materials for couples; • Interactive whiteboard allows you to save time at different stages of the game. This is very important in conditions of intensive training, where the lack of time is noticeable; • Interactive whiteboard gives the opportunity to repeatedly use the prepared material: when

explaining new material; when checking homework and thematic repetition; • Operational control Knowledge, Skill, Skills and availability of feedback; • The Board allows you to create and improve your own collections of materials for pairs. • The digital resources of the interactive whiteboard are fascinating, so students are more attentive in pairs; • The use of interactive whiteboard stimulates the activity of students for whom the Russian language is not native in pairs, the process of memorization and repetition is enhanced. On the basis of the interactive whiteboard, it is possible to carry out a communicative game in the form of communication (debate), reasoning or work in small groups, since this is an activity in which social relations between people are recreated outside the conditions of direct activity. Communicative games contribute to the realization of such goals as diagnosis, systematization, development of logical thinking, auditory memory and attention, education of interest in the subject. Technologies of communicative games are characterized by such features as efficiency, algorithm city, project ability, integrity, manageability, democrat city and effectiveness. In the process of organizing these games, we often use a group form, including 5-6 people in the micro group, distribute responsibilities, discuss the stages of tasks, choose a leader, create a positive emotional atmosphere of cooperation. For example, in the form of a business game, we conducted classes on the preparation of a verbal portrait of the suspect.

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